

CHARTER WEBSITE AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

CHARTER Deliverable D7.2

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 48 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Leading Author: Coordination team / LAY

Contributing partners: -

Co-financed by the Connecting Europe Facility of the European Union

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Due Submission Date: 30/09/2020

Actual Submission Date: 30/09/2020

Revised version submitted: 30/06/2022

Status	
Draft	
Final	x

Type		
R	Document, report	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
OTHER		

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Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission services)	

Revision history

Date(s)	Lead author(s)	Comments
15.9.2020	Philip Burgess and Markku Heikkilä	1 st draft version
30.9.2020	CHARTER coordination team	Final version, submitted
30.6.2022	CHARTER coordination team	Final version (v2), revised according the comments given during the first review, submitted

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Communication tools

Website

The CHARTER Arctic project has a project website (www.charter-arctic.org) which is hosted in partnership with the University of Lapland, and created with the open source Wordpress platform.

The website is the main “face” of the project and with that, a key communication tool. The challenge is to make the website usable and useful for first-time visitors and those with wide knowledge of the project.

The project website went live already in May 2020. The website gives a comprehensive overview of the project. The landing page gives a brief general language overview of the project, its goals and work package structure, in addition to the institutional partners and funders. Also from the landing page there are downloadable pdfs that give a 2-page overview of the project in simple language, in addition to a 28 page scientific summary.

The website has links to social media channels: a Twitter account, a YouTube channel (shared with the Arctic Centre, University of Lapland) a Facebook page (via the Arctic Centre, University of Lapland). CHARTER utilizes the existing YouTube and Facebook channels of the Arctic Centre in order to make full use of existing networks.

There are simple language translations of the project structure and objectives in the following languages: English, Russian, Finnish, Norwegian, Swedish, North Sámi, Inari Sámi, Nenets, German, French and Bulgarian.

There are the following menu links from the landing page: News (project news), Work Packages (the broad outline of the 7 different Work Packages, their content and participants), Partners (a map showing and linking to the different institutional partners and the participants), Publications (links and downloads to all the project publications, working papers and policy papers), Image Gallery (an overview of

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images from various fieldwork sites), Video Gallery (interviews hosted on YouTube with all the Work Package leaders and a handful of new researchers), Secrets of Snow (with a Finnish sub menu Lumen Salaisuuksia Ratkomassa) which is an ancillary CHARTER product that was created in response to the challenges caused by the pandemic. A simplified protocol was developed for the analysis of snow pit characteristics). The final menu item is an About link with our contact details which also has a sub menu item with an Internal password protected page for project participants, and a Privacy Policy link.

The landing page has a customizable image slider with links to highlighted content, below which is a static image box links with links to News/Partners/Work Packages/Publications.

On the sidebar there is a number of widgets. One is an option to sign up for the CHARTER Newsletter (all previous newsletters are available to view on the Publications page. Next is a shared CHARTER project calendar. There is a secondary link for the CHARTER Internal page for project researchers and finally there is an embedded feed of our Twitter account.

At the footer of the landing page, there are links to the project funder, the EU Polar Cluster and a sister project, AROSS, the Arctic Rain on Snow Study. Below the footer there is a Contact Us link and Privacy Policy link.

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Twitter and other social media

The CHARTER project maintains a Twitter account which is accessible at @CharterArctic. The project uses the CHARTER Twitter account to outreach project deliverables, news, fieldwork and through the active use of Twitter lists to monitor and retweet the work of all the CHARTER researchers that are on Twitter. Generally the CHARTER project tweets and/or retweets several times a week.

Partner institutes and individual researchers are advised to retweet and use #CHARTERArctic whenever possible to enhance the message.

The CHARTER project has a YouTube playlist which is hosts on the Arctic Centre, University of Lapland YouTube channel. By the end of 2021, the playlist had 19 videos which included interviews with CHARTER project leader, CHARTER work package leaders, CHARTER researchers and several young researchers. The playlist is available to view here:

https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6SojJRvu9GT_AbAQ-HQONh5Bl8W1xTtK

Newsletter

The need of a newsletter became obvious once the project had started. A newsletter is a tool to easily summarize what the project has been doing, what are the recent milestones and major news. A newsletter also gives a platform to publish things that as such would not work as individual website news or press releases, such as project event summaries.

The newsletter comes out twice a year during the project life span and it can be subscribed from the website. While the subscription numbers are not expected to be very high, the newsletter also serves as an easily accessible project memory on the website: one can scroll the published issues and see where and how the project has been going.

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Media

Press releases are traditional but however quite ineffective ways of reaching to the media. When publishing major results, project-wide press releases are a necessary tool. During normal operations of the project, the tools can be more targeted. A good way is to approach directly identified media or journalists, basing on the theme or location of the activity.